

Stigmasterol from the flowers of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* (DC.) Backer ex K. Heyne (Fabaceae) — Isolation, spectral properties and quantum chemical studies

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Stigmasterol, a biologically potent phytosterol, has been isolated and identified first-time from the flowers of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* (DC.) Backer ex K. Heyne (Family: Fabaceae) based on detailed spectral studies including 1D- and 2D-NMR. A thorough computational study on the molecular features, vibrational spectra and many other descriptors like HOMO, LUMO, MESP surfaces of the title molecule have been performed. The calculated geometrical parameters are found to be in good harmony with the experimental values. The vibrational modes have been assigned on the basis of potential energy distribution as calculated by VEDA software package and agree well with the corresponding FTIR numbers. Using Gauge independent Orbital method, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR shifts have been calculated and found to be in good correlation with the experimental results. Global reactivity descriptors and thermodynamic parameters of the molecule have also been calculated.

Keywords: Stigmasterol, *Peltophorum pterocarpum*, structure, spectral studies, quantum chemical studies.

Introduction

Stigmasterol (**1**; Fig. 1) is an important member of the steroidal class of natural products with significant biological and pharmaceutical promise¹. This phytosterol² is reported to act as a precursor in the synthesis of progesterone, and as an intermediate in the biosynthesis of hormones such as androgens, estrogens, and corticoids³ as well as in the synthesis of vitamin D₃⁴. Stigmasterol, with a wide range of beneficial metabolic and therapeutic actions on living systems, has been evaluated to exhibiting many pharmacological properties, such as antiosteoarthritic⁵, cytotoxic and antitumor activity⁶, hypo-glycemic⁷, antioxidant⁸ and anti-inflammatory activity⁹. In continuation of our works on medicinal plants¹⁰, we have recently found *Peltophorum pterocarpum* (DC.) Backer ex K. Heyne (Family: Fabaceae) a new natural source of this biologically potent phytosterol **1**.

P. pterocarpum is an important plant used in traditional system of medicines to treat many diseases, such as dysentery, stomatitis, insomnia, skin disorders and ringworm infections¹¹. Flowers of *P. pterocarpum* find useful application

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of stigmasterol (**1**).

as a lotion for eye troubles, muscular pains and sores, and also as an astringent to cure or relieve intestinal disorders¹². Extract from its flowers is used in treating insomnia¹³. Earlier phytochemical studies with this plant reported on the presence of a variety of chemical constituents including tannins, terpenoids and flavonoids¹⁴. In this communication, we first-time report the occurrence of stigmasterol (**1**) in *P. pterocarpum* isolated from the extract of its flowers and characterized based on its detailed spectral properties. We have also performed a detailed study of various quantum chemi-

cal aspects of this phytosterol **1** using Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT). Vibrational spectral analysis is an established technique today¹⁵ in determining the molecular structure of a compound and quantum chemical computation of the vibrational spectral feature of a molecule has now become a usual practice by the researchers due to its much accuracy and consistency to describe the experimental findings. Therefore, we have also been motivated to explain vibrational spectral features of this molecule in this communication with a comparison between the calculated and experimentally recorded FT-IR spectrum. The molecular properties of stigmasterol are discussed with the help of quantum chemical descriptors such as HOMO, LUMO and MESP etc.

Experimental

Chemicals and instrumentation:

Analytical grade chemicals were used in this study. Solvents were dried as per the literature methods¹⁶ before use.

Melting point recorded on a Chemiline CL-726 melting point apparatus is uncorrected. The infrared spectra (range: 4000–400 cm^{-1} scan: 25, resolution: 2.0) were recorded on FT-IR-8400S (with MCT detector) using KBr disc. ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, DEPT-135, HMQC and HMBC spectra were obtained on a Bruker DRX (400 MHz) spectrometer using CDCl_3 as the solvent. TMS was used as internal standard in recording NMR spectra. Mass spectra (TOF-MS) were measured on a QTOF Micro mass spectrometer. Elemental analysis was performed with a Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II elemental analyzer instrument. Chromatography was carried on silica gel columns (Merck 60–120 mesh) and TLC was performed on silica gel 60 F254 (Merck) plates.

Plant materials:

Fresh flowers of *Peltophorum pterocarpum* (DC.) Backer ex K. Heyne (Family: Fabaceae) were at and around Santiniketan, West Bengal, India, and identified by Dr. H. R. Chowdhury (Botany Department, Visva-Bharati University). A voucher specimen is preserved in the Laboratory of Natural Products and Organic Synthesis of this University.

Extraction and isolation of stigmasterol (1):

Air-dried and finely grinded flowers of *P. pterocarpum* (3.5 kg) were extracted with ethanol at room temperature; the

cold ethanol extract (~4.5 L) was then concentrated under reduced pressure with the help of a rotary evaporator to yield a greenish semi-solid mass (~100 g). This residue was partitioned between a mixture of distilled water (200 ml) and petrol ether (60–80°; 500 ml), successively repeated for 3 times. The combined organic layer was evaporated out to have a crude mass (21 g), which was then subjected to column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh, 420 g). The column was eluted with petrol ether (2 L) and then successively with petrol ether-ethyl acetate mixtures (2 L each) at respective ratio of 99:1 (v/v) and 98:2 (v/v). All these eluents did not afford any appreciable mass. The next eluent of relatively higher polarity, petrol-ethyl acetate (97:3), afforded the steroidal constituent, stigmasterol (**1**) as white powder solid (97 mg).

Stigmasterol (**1**). Yield: 0.003% (97 mg), white powder, m.p. 161–163°C, responded positively to the Liebermann-Burchardt test; FT-IR (KBr): 3447 (OH), 2941 (C-H), 1652 (C=C), 1641 (C=C), 1454, 1369, 1238, 1045, 964, 865, 789, 733, 611, 548 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3), ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3), DEPT-135, 2D-NMR (HMQC and HMBC) are presented in Table 1 and described in the text; HR-TOF-MS: m/z 435.3607 ($\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{ONa}$, $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ requires 435.3603). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$: C, 84.40; H, 11.72; Found: C, 84.48; H, 11.71.

Computational methods:

In the present study all the theoretical calculations of the stigmasterol (**1**) have been carried out employing Gaussian 09 suite of program¹⁷ using the B3LYP/6-31+G (d,p) level of theory to envisage all the molecular properties. The geometry optimization of stigmasterol has been carried out by Becke's three parameter exchange term combined with the gradient-corrected correlation functional of Lee, Yang and Parr¹⁸. The absence of any imaginary frequency in the vibrational spectrum obtained after the calculation clearly demonstrates the minimum energy conformation so obtained.

Results and discussion

Isolation and structural elucidation of stigmasterol (1) based on spectral studies:

Stigmasterol (**1**) was isolated from the petrol ether (60–80°C) fraction of ethanolic extract of *P. pterocarpum* flowers as white powder (m.p. 161–163°C). Elemental analyses and

Table 1. 1D- and 2D-NMR data of phytosterol **1**

Carbon	¹ H (ppm/δ)	¹³ C (ppm/δ)	DEPT-135	HMQC (¹ H- ¹³ C correlation)	HMBC (¹ H- ¹³ C correlation)
C-1	1.87–1.84 (1H, m, H-1a), 1.09–1.08 (1H, m, H-1b)	37.24	CH ₂	δ 37.24 (C-1) vs δ 1.87–1.84 (H-1a) and δ 1.09–1.08 (H-1b)	δ 1.87–1.84 (H-1a) vs δ 71.73 (C-3)
C-2	1.87–1.84 (1H, m, H-2a), 1.55–1.43 (1H, m, H-2b)	31.61	CH ₂	δ 31.61 (C-2) vs δ 1.87–1.84 (H-2a) and δ 1.55–1.43 (H-2b)	–
C-3	3.56–3.51 (1H, m, H-3)	71.73	CH	δ 71.73 (C-3) vs δ 3.56–3.51 (H-3)	–
C-4	2.31–2.21 (2H, m, H-4)	42.26	CH ₂	δ 42.26 (C-4) vs δ 2.31–2.21 (H-4)	δ 2.31–2.21 (H-4) vs δ 31.61 (C-2), 71.73 (C-3), 140.73 (C-5), 121.65 (C-6), 36.48 (C-10)
C-5	–	140.73	C	–	–
C-6	5.36 (1H, brs, H-6)	121.65	CH	δ 121.65 (C-6) vs δ 5.36 (H-6)	δ 5.36 (H-6) vs δ 31.87 (C-7), 29.15 (C-8), 36.48 (C-10)
C-7	1.55–1.43 (2H, m, H-7)	31.87	CH ₂	δ 31.87 (C-7) vs δ 1.55–1.43 (H-7)	δ 1.55–1.43 (H-7) vs δ 24.33 (C-15), 29.15 (C-8)
C-8	1.76–1.66 (1H, m, H-8)	29.15	CH	δ 29.15 (C-8) vs δ 1.76–1.66 (H-8)	–
C-9	1.04–1.02 (1H, m, H-9)	50.14	CH	δ 50.14 (C-9) vs δ 1.04–1.02 (H-9)	δ 1.04–1.02 (H-9) vs δ 37.24 (C-1), 140.73 (C-5)
C-10	–	36.48	C	–	–
C-11	1.55–1.43 (2H, m, H-11)	21.05	CH ₂	δ 21.05 (C-11) vs δ 1.55–1.43 (H-11)	–
C-12	2.04–2.01 (2H, m, H-12)	39.75	CH ₂	δ 39.75 (C-12) vs δ 2.04–2.01 (H-12)	–
C-13	–	42.18	C	–	–
C-14	1.04–1.02 (1H, m, H-14)	56.84	CH	δ 56.84 (C-14) vs δ 1.04–1.02 (H-14)	–
C-15	1.55–1.43 (1H, m, H-15a), 1.04–1.02 (1H, m, H-15b)	24.33	CH ₂	δ 24.33 (C-15) vs δ 1.55–1.43 (H-15a) and δ 1.04–1.02 (H-15b)	δ 1.55–1.43 (H-15a) vs δ 31.87 (C-7)
C-16	1.76–1.66 (1H, m, H-16a), 1.55–1.43 (1H, m, H-16b)	28.88	CH ₂	δ 28.88 (C-16) vs δ 1.76–1.66 (H-16a) and δ 1.55–1.43 (H-16b)	–
C-17	1.04–1.02 (1H, m, H-17)	55.93	CH	δ 55.93 (C-17) vs δ 1.04–1.02 (H-17)	δ 1.04–1.02 (H-17) vs δ 40.46 (C-20), 138.27 (C-22)
C-18	0.84 (3H, s, H-18)	12.21	CH ₃	δ 12.21 (C-18) vs δ 0.84 (H-18)	δ 0.84 (H-18) vs δ 31.87 (C-7), 29.15 (C-8), 28.88 (C-16), 21.19 (C-21)
C-19	0.86 (3H, s, H-19)	19.36	CH ₃	δ 19.36 (C-19) vs δ 0.86 (H-19)	δ 0.86 (H-19) vs δ 21.05 (C-11), 29.15 (C-8), 31.61 (C-2), 50.14 (C-9)
C-20	2.01–2.04 (1H, m, H-20)	40.46	CH	δ 40.46 (C-20) vs δ 2.01–2.04 (H-20)	–
C-21	0.94 (3H, d, H-21)	21.19	CH ₃	δ 21.19 (C-21) vs δ 0.94 (H-21)	δ 0.94 (H-21) vs δ 55.93 (C-17)

Table-1 (contd.)

C-22	5.14–5.17 (1H, m, H-22)	138.27	CH	δ 38.27 (C-22) vs δ 5.14–5.17 (H-22)	δ 5.14–5.17 (H-22) vs δ 40.46 (C-20), 51.21 (C-24)
C-23	5.04–5.06 (1H, m, H-23)	129.25	CH	δ 29.25 (C-23) vs δ 5.04–5.06 (H-23)	–
C-24	1.43 (1H, m, H-24)	51.21	CH	δ 51.21 (C-24) vs δ 1.43 (H-24)	–
C-25	1.55–1.54 (1H, m, H-25)	39.66	CH	δ 39.66 (C-25) vs δ 1.55–1.54 (H-25)	–
C-26	0.81 (3H, d, H-26)	19.78	CH ₃	δ 19.78 (C-26) vs δ 0.81 (H-26)	δ 0.81 (H-26) vs δ 25.37 (C-28)
C-27	0.70 (3H, d, H-27)	21.19	CH ₃	δ 21.19 (C-27) vs δ 0.70 (H-27)	δ 0.70 (H-27) vs δ 39.66 (C-25), 55.93 (C-17)
C-28	1.29–1.23 (2H, m, H-28)	25.37	CH ₂	δ 25.37 (C-28) vs δ 1.29–1.23 (H-28)	δ 1.29–1.23 (H-28) vs δ 12.01 (C-29)
C-29	1.17 (3H, t, H-29)	12.01	CH ₃	δ 12.01 (C-29) vs δ 1.17 (H-29)	δ 1.17 (H-29) vs δ 19.78 (C-26)

DEPT: Distortionless Enhancement by Polarization; HMQC: Heteronuclear Multiple-Quantum Correlation; HMBC: Heteronuclear Multiple Bond Correlation.

HR-TOF-MS ($[M + Na]^+$, 435.3607) data confirmed its molecular formula as C₂₉H₄₈O. Positive response towards Libermann-Burchardt reaction by the compound indicated its steroidal nature. The infrared absorption bands in the IR spectrum of **1** at 3447 cm⁻¹ (free OH), 2941 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic C-H stretching) and 1652, 1641, 1454 and 964 cm⁻¹ (di- and tri-substituted double bonds) are in accordance with the presence of an unsaturated sterol moiety within its molecule¹⁹. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **1** recorded (i) one triplet at δ 1.17 (3H, t, $J = 9.2$ and 9.6 Hz) for a primary methyl group at C-29; (ii) three doublets at δ 0.70 (3H, d, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 0.81 (3H, d, $J = 6.4$ Hz) and 0.94 (3H, d, $J = 6$ Hz) for three secondary methyl groups, respectively at C-27, C-26 and C-21; (iii) two singlets at δ 0.84 (3H, s) and 0.86 (3H, s) for two tertiary methyls at C-18 and C-19, respectively; (iv) one multiplet at δ 3.51–3.56 (1H, m) for the α -oriented carbinol-methine (>CHOH) proton; (v) another two multiplets at δ 5.04–5.06 (1H, m) and 5.14–5.17 (1H, m) ascribable to two vinyl protons (*trans*-oriented) attached with the C₂₂-C₂₃ di-substituted *trans*-double bond; (vi) a broad singlet at δ 5.36 (1H, br s) for one more vinyl proton at C-6 linked with the tri-substituted double bond between C₅-C₆. The remaining protons appeared as complex multiplets between δ 1.23–2.31 for methylene protons of the steroidal skeleton. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of **1** recorded desired carbon signals for twenty nine different carbons. The ¹³C-chemical shift values and their respective DEPT-135 analysis (Table 1) clearly supported its

steroidal skeleton bearing one primary methyl (C-29 at δ 12.01), three secondary methyls (C-21 and C-27 at δ 21.19 (2C) and C-26 at δ 19.78), two tertiary methyls (C-18 at δ 12.21 and C-19 at δ 19.36), nine methylenes, eleven methines and three quaternary carbons. The appearance of the ¹³C NMR signals at δ 71.73, 138.27 and 129.25 and 140.73 and 121.65 are supportive of the presence of a >CHOH moiety at C-3 (OH group with β -orientation), a di-substituted C-C double bond at C₂₂-C₂₃ and a tri-substituted C-C double bond at C₅-C₆, respectively within the molecule of **1**. All these FT-IR and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data obtained from the high-resolution NMR spectrophotometer for stigmasterol isolated from *P. pterocarpum* flowers were found to be in full agreement with those reported in literature^{2,6a,e,f}. Fig. 2 shows ¹H, ¹³C and DEPT-135 NMR spectra of the phytosterol **1**. In addition, the ¹H and ¹³C NMR assignments for the molecule received excellent confirmation from its HMQC (heteronuclear multiple-quantum correlation) spectral analysis (Table 1). The isolate **1** was, thus, unequivocally identified as stigmasterol [(3 β ,22E,24S)-stigmasta-5,22-dien-3-ol] on the basis of detailed spectral and physical properties and as per our literature search, this is the first report of its occurrence from *P. pterocarpum*. We also studied HMBC (heteronuclear multiple bond correlation) spectral properties of the isolated compound, and the observed long-range hetero-bond correlations (Table 1) as shown in Fig. 3 firmly supports the deduced structure **1**.

Fig. 2c. DEPT-135 spectrum of 1.

Fig. 3. Selected HMBC interactions for 1.

Theoretical studies:

Molecular geometry:

The optimized geometry of stigmasterol with properly labeled atoms is shown in Fig. 4. The optimized structural pa-

rameters (bond length, bond angle) calculated by employing B3LYP at 6-31+G (d,p) basis set are given in Table 2. The title compound exhibits the C_1 point group symmetry. The vibrational spectra calculated by DFT using (B3LYP) level have been performed making use of the optimized parameters. The calculated values of C-H and C-C bond lengths as listed in the Table 2 match reasonably well with the reported values in the literature²⁰.

Analysis of vibrational spectra and FT-IR spectra:

The title compound with 78 atoms belongs to C_1 point group symmetry; the molecule thus has maximum number of potentially active observable fundamentals equal to 228 ($3N-6$)²¹. The graphical interface of the Gauss-view program²² assisted beautifully in the assignments of the calculated vibrational frequencies. The potential energy distribution is calculated using VEDA 4 software program²³. The DFT hybrid B3LYP functional tends to overrate the force constant at the exact equilibrium geometry and thus the calculated

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (angstroms) and bond angles (degrees) of stigmasterol calculated at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) level

Parameter	Calculated	Parameter	Calculated	Parameter	Calculated
C1-C2	1.518	C1-C6	1.529	C1-H31	1.097
C1-H32	1.096	C2-C3	1.530	C2-O18	1.424
C2-H33	1.103	C3-H34	1.097	C10-C14	1.542
C10-H42	1.103	C11-C12	1.542	C11-C15	1.535
C11-H43	1.104	C12-C13	1.532	C20-H59	1.093
C21-C22	1.541	C21-C23	1.515	C21-H60	1.102
C22-H61	1.096	C22-H62	1.094	C22-H63	1.092
C23-C24	1.337	C28-H71	1.095	C28-H72	1.097
C28-H73	1.093	C29-C30	1.530	C29-H74	1.098
C29-H75	1.095	C30-H76	1.095	C30-H77	1.096
C2-C1-C6	110.9	C2-C1-H32	109.4	C6-C1-H31	111.2
H31-C1-H32	106.6	C1-C2-O18	107.6	C3-C2-O18	111.9
O18-C2-H33	109.6	C2-C3-H35	107.0	C4-C3-H34	109.4
C3-C4-C5	116.6	C5-C4-C7	122.9	C6-C5-C10	108.6
C5-C6-H36	109.5	C5-C6-H37	108.1	H39-C8-H40	105.2
C8-C9-H41	107.8	C10-C9-C11	109.5	C10-C9-H41	109.3
C11-C9-H41	109.4	C5-C10-H42	105.8	C9-C10-C14	112.5
C12-C11-C15	104.1	C12-C11-H43	105.1	H46-C14-H47	105.8
C11-C15-C16	104.2	C11-C15-H48	112.3	C11-C15-H49	110.7
C15-C16-C17	106.1	C15-C16-H50	111.8	C2-C18-H53	108.7
C26-C27-H68	110.2	C26-C27-H69	112.5	C26-C27-H70	111.1
C26-C28-H72	110.9	C26-C28-H73	112.1	H71-C28-H72	107.4
H71-C28-H73	107.6	H72-C28-H73	108.0	H77-C30-H78	107.4

Fig. 4. Optimized structure of stigmasterol.

frequencies have been scaled by the factor of 0.9648 as put forward by Merrick *et al.*²⁴. The comparison of scaled frequency with experimental values suggests that B3LYP method shows a reasonably good agreement with the ex-

perimentally observed spectra. The FT-IR spectra of the molecule are recorded by Shimadzu spectrophotometer in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} using samples in KBr pellet. The experimental and calculated frequencies along with their par-

ticular assignments are listed in Table 3. The experimental and calculated IR spectra are shown in Fig. 5.

The O-H stretching vibration calculated at wave number 3718 cm^{-1} is a pure stretching mode with the PED contribution of 100% and is consistent with the values reported in the literature²⁵. The other O-H vibrations such as scissoring and skeletal torsion are observed at very low frequency (below 500 cm^{-1}).

The C-H stretching vibration of the molecular framework appeared in region 3055 , 2941 and 2864 cm^{-1} in FTIR spectra and are also in conformity with the literature values²⁶.

The C-H in and out of plane-bending frequencies are very useful in characterizing molecular skeleton modes²⁷. The C-H in plane-bending vibrations for compound **1** appeared as strong band in FTIR spectrum at 1045 cm^{-1} and at 1238 cm^{-1} as a medium band in the FTIR spectrum, respectively. The C-H out of plane-bending vibrations were recorded as strongly coupled vibrations in the region $1000\text{--}750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ²⁸. The molecular structure showed the presence of C-C stretching vibration in the region $1678\text{--}966\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and in FTIR at 1653 , 1641 , 1045 and 964 cm^{-1} which are also in agreement with the reported values²⁹. Some other C-C vibrational

Table 3. Vibrational analysis of some selected modes of stigmasterol calculated at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) level

Frequency (cm^{-1})		Intensity	FTIR	Assignment (PED>15%)
Calc.	Scal.	IR	Freq.	
3854	3718	22.0	3634	$\nu(\text{O18-H53})(100)$
3163	3051	30.1	3055	$\nu(\text{C24-H65})(98)$
3150	3039	20.5	–	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C22-H62})(88)$
3145	3034	51.2	–	$R[\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C7-H38})(97)]$
3139	3028	46.1	–	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C20-H58})(93)$
3119	3009	50.4	–	$R[\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C15-H48})(69)]$
3100	2991	10.7	–	$R[\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C16-H51})(81)]$
3075	2967	38.2	–	$R[\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C16-H50})(89)]$
3060	2952	30.4	–	$R[\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C8-H40})(19)] + \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C19-H54})(22)$
3046	2939	52.8	2941	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C30-H77})(59)$
3027	2920	37.1	–	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C3-H34})(97)$
2970	2865	9.1	2864	$R[\nu(\text{C11-H43})(96)]$
1740	1678	2.8	1653	$R[\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C4-C7})(73)]$
1731	1670	1.0	1641	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C23-C24})(71)$
1521	1467	5.5	–	$\sigma(\text{H49-C15-H48})(60)$
1507	1454	3.0	1454	$\sigma(\text{H51-C16-H50})(23)$
1489	1437	4.6	–	$\sigma(\text{H49-C15-H48})(19)$
1416	1366	10.4	1369	$\omega(\text{H68-C27-H70})(40) + \omega(\text{H70-C27-H69})(26)$
1366	1318	2.2	1319	$R[\tau_{\text{o}}(\text{H43-C11-C15-C16})(16)]$
1318	1272	1.7	–	$R[\tau_{\text{i}}(\text{H39-C8-C7-C4})(16)]$
1284	1239	5.0	1238	$\sigma(\text{H64-C23-H24})(16)$
1079	1041	10.6	1045	$R[\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C10-C14})(16)]$
1001	966	3.7	964	$R[\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C16-C15})(23)]$
816	787	2.9	789	$R[\tau_{\text{i}}(\text{H35-C3-C4-C5})(16)]$
767	740	4.7	733	$\tau_{\text{i}}(\text{H75-C29-C25-C26})(18)$
544	525	0.5	538	$R[\tau_{\text{o}}(\text{C15-C9-C12-C11})(16)]$
452	436	1.2	428	$R[\sigma(\text{C10-C14-C13})(16)]$

Abbreviations used ν_{as} : asymmetric stretching; ν_{s} : symmetric stretching; σ : scissoring; ρ : rocking, τ_{o} : out of plane torsion; τ_{i} : in the plane torsion; R: carbon ring.

Note: The PED distribution less than 15% are neglected for the sake of calculation.

Fig. 5. Combined theoretical and experimental IR spectra of stigmasterol.

modes are found in lower wavenumber region along with other intertwined modes. Most of the C-C modes are comparatively stronger than the C-H modes.

HOMO-LUMO and MESP surfaces analysis:

Excitation properties and the ability of electron transport of a molecule can be well-predicted qualitatively from studying its highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and lowest molecular orbitals (LUMOs)³⁰. The chemical stability of a molecule can also be well-justified from these two molecular orbitals associated with electron donation and acceptance³¹. The intra-molecular charge transfer is an index of bioactivity of a biomolecule, which depends upon the frontier molecular orbital gap. The HOMO and LUMO plots of the title compound are shown in Fig. 6. The energies of HOMO and LUMO of stigmasterol was calculated by using B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) method and the corresponding energy gap for stigmasterol

is 6.32 eV.

The molecular electrostatic potential (MESP) of a molecule offers an idea on its localized electron density and thus helps in pin pointing the sites for electrophilic and nucleophilic reactions³². It also gives an idea of the possible relation of the molecular structure with physicochemical properties³³. The MESP plot was calculated at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) and is shown in Fig. 6. The variations in the surface electrostatic potential of molecule 1 are expressed by different colors, in the increasing order of the potential red < orange < yellow < green < blue (blue indicates the most electropositive i.e. electron poor region and red indicates the most electronegative region i.e. electron rich region). The MESP plot shows that the most electropositive region is located over oxygen single bonded with hydrogen, which effectively acts as an electron acceptor within the molecule. It can be further mentioned herein that the mapped MESP over a single layer is not enough to indicate as to which ligands region is more susceptible to an oncoming electrophile and a more careful analysis of the contour map of ligand is required to get a better insight.

Global reactivity descriptors and thermodynamic parameters:

The electronic parameters such as ionization potential (I), electron affinity (A), absolute electronegativity (χ) and chemical hardness (η) of stigmasterol were calculated at B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) level. The descriptors like ionization potential (I) and electron affinity (A) for the molecule were calculated using the Koopmans' theorem. Other parameters η and χ were calculated by using finite-difference approximations³⁴ as $\chi = 1/2(I + A)$ and $\eta = 1/2(I - A)$. The chemical

Table 4. Electronic and thermodynamic parameters of stigmasterol calculated at B3LYP/6-31+G (d,p) level

Electronic parameter	Stigmasterol	Thermodynamic parameter	Stigmasterol
I (eV)	6.43	ZPE (kcal/mol)	450.67
A (eV)	0.11	E (kcal/mol)	470.64
E_g (eV)	6.32	C_v (cal/mol-K)	127.92
χ (eV)	3.32	S (cal/mol-K)	198.10
η (eV)	3.16	G (kcal/mol)	412.15
μ (a.u.)	1.56	H (kcal/mol)	471.20
S	0.15	ω (eV)	1.74

Fig. 6. HOMO-LUMO and Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MESP) surface of stigmasterol.

descriptors were calculated as below³⁵,

Global softness, $S = 1/2\eta$ and electrophilicity, $\omega = \chi^2/2\eta$

The calculated electronic parameters for stigmasterol are listed in Table 3. The thermodynamic parameters viz. zero point energy (ZPE), thermal energy at room temperature (E), heat capacity (C_v) and entropy (S) for the title compound are also calculated and listed in Table 4. These parameters are

often used to describe chemical reactivity of a molecule and in getting an idea about the reaction paths.

¹H and ¹³C NMR analyses:

The geometry for both stigmasterol and tetramethylsilane (TMS) has been fully optimized. GIAO approach at B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) method³⁶ has been implemented to calculate the ¹H and ¹³C NMR chemical shifts for the molecule. Chemi-

cal shift of any 'x' proton (δ_x) equals to the difference between isotropic magnetic shielding (IMS) of TMS and proton (x) [i.e. $\delta_x = \text{IMS}_{\text{TMS}} - \text{IMS}_x$]. Hence, chemical shift δ for a methine proton (CH) proton will appear approximately 3.0–4.0 ppm downfield from the corresponding methylene/methane proton chemical shifts ($\text{CH} > \text{CH}_2 > \text{CH}_3$) due to the difference in shielding effect. The calculated and experimental ^1H NMR chemical shifts (δ/ppm) of compound **1** are given in Table 5³⁷.

The calculated and experimental ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (δ/ppm) of the title compound are given in Table 5. The ^{13}C NMR chemical shift of C24 and C4 atoms are 122.0 and 141.3 ppm, respectively. This is primarily due to the decrease in electron donating or shielding ability of the attached atoms³⁸. From Tables 4 and 5, it is clear that there is no consi-

Table 5. Calculated and experimental ^1H NMR chemical shifts (δ/ppm) of stigmasterol in CDCl_3 solvent

Atom	$\delta_{\text{calc.}}$	$\delta_{\text{exp.}}$	Assignment
H33	3.60	3.56	[1H, m, -CHOH]
H38	5.99	5.36	[1H, br s, -C=CH-]
H58	0.76	0.84	[3H, s, CH_3]
H61	0.98	0.94	[3H, d, CH_3]
H64	5.61	5.17	[1H, m, -CH=CH-]
H70	0.68	0.70	[3H, s, CH_3]
H78	1.01	0.81	[3H, s, CH_3]

Fig. 7. Correlation graph between the experimental and calculated ^1H NMR chemical shift of molecule.

Fig. 8. Correlation graph between the experimental and calculated ^{13}C NMR chemical shift of molecule.

derable difference of chemical shift between experimental and calculated data. The correlation graphs between experimental and calculated chemical shift of ^1H and ^{13}C NMR with linear fitting are also shown in Figs. 7 and 8 and the corresponding value of R^2 (coefficient of determination) are 0.9952 and 0.9997, respectively.

Table 6. Calculated and experimental ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (δ/ppm) of stigmasterol in CDCl_3 solvent

Atom No.	$\delta_{\text{calc.}}$	$\delta_{\text{exp.}}$	Assignment
C4	141.3	140.7	[1C, - CH_3]
C5	42.4	42.2	[3C, R(-C)]
C6	40.5	39.7	[2C, - CH_2]
C10	51.4	51.2	[3C, R(-CH)]
C15	25.7	25.4	[2C, - CH_2]
C16	24.7	24.3	[2C, - CH_2]
C17	56.0	55.9	[3C, -CH]
C19	20.3	19.7	[1C, - CH_3]
C22	18.0	19.4	[1C, - CH_3]
C24	122.0	121.6	[3C, R(-CH)]
C29	30.7	31.6	[2C, - CH_2]

Conclusions

In this work, stigmasterol has been isolated and characterized as one of the chemical constituents of the traditionally used medicinal plant, *Peltophorum pterocarpum* for the first-time, based on detailed spectral studies including FT-

IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, DEPT-135, HMQC, HMBC and HRMS. Density Functional Theory (DFT) has been employed for exhaustive theoretical studies on the molecular structure, vibrational spectra, HOMO, LUMO, MESP surfaces and reactivity descriptor of this plant-derived natural molecule. The vibrational spectrum of the title compound has been calculated and the scaled infrared wavenumbers are found to be in good agreement with the experimentally reported values. The calculated ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra are also in good agreement with experimental data. The HOMO-LUMO and MESP analysis for the title compound is carried out and presumably they can provide an insight to measure molecular stability and reactivity of the compound. Results of the global reactivity descriptors and thermodynamic parameters for the molecule are helpful in assuming its chemical reactivity. Local reactivity descriptors are also determined in order to offer an insight into the relative reactivity of different atoms in the molecule. It can be said with conviction that for the largest value of descriptor the molecule is to be attacked by a soft reagent, while the value becomes smaller when attacked by a hard reagent. Our present study, thus, offers a thorough insight into the experimental and theoretical aspects of such a promising naturally occurring steroid molecule and should certainly pave a way for the future research.

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